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Obj.: Appendix for the Application of Ms Lemenkova Polina for the *International Visegrad Fund (IVF) post-MSc Scholarship* for the research stay in *Charles University, Faculty of Science, Department of Physical Geography and Geoecology*, Prague from the 01st of March 2011 until 01st of August 2011 (during 5 months).

Detailed Working Plan

for the post-MSc research stay of the visiting PhD-student Lemenkova Polina in *Charles University, Faculty of Science, Department of Physical Geography and Geoecology* from the 01 March 2011 until 01 August 2011, under the supervision of RNDr. Vít Vilímek, CSc.

Theme of the Research Project: Analysis of slope movements dynamics in Czech Republic

Region of Interest: Bohemian Massif, Western Carpathians
Research main aims: 1) Geomorphological modeling of selected areas of highlands
2) Analysis of slope movements dynamic

Expected results:

- One (1) scientific article for the publication in peer-reviewed international or Czech national scientific journal in Earth sciences, showing and resuming the results of our work
- Thematic geomorphological maps of the Bohemian Massif showing the dynamic of slope movements in the past 10-20 years
- Report for the *IVF* resuming our work and results

§ 1. 01 March 2011 – 01 April. Studies of possible sources for our research

1. Using numerous materials from both the main Library of *Charles University* and the archives of the Department of Geology we plan to study particularities of physical geography, geomorphological and geological conditions in the Bohemian Massif including hydro-geomorphological and soil characteristics, river system, geological features and vegetation coverage of the Bohemian Massif..

Resources: all possible available materials from the *Faculty of Science, Department of Physical Geography and Geoecology* - detailed maps, books, reports and relevant articles concerning our region of interest. For the analysis of the slope movements we plan to use satellite images for different dates using software *Erdas Imagine* or *ENVI*, if available. Main software for our research work is *ArcGIS 9.3*

2. Detailed studies of the geomorphological and hydrogeological conditions (incl. indirect factors) in the Bohemian Massif region: groundwater flow, irrigation, plant transpiration and soil salinization using all possible materials.

Resources: mostly the Library of the Charles University and materials from the *Faculty of Science, Department of Physical Geography and Geoecology*.

§ 2. 01 April 2011–01 May. Analysis of the slope movements dynamics in Czech Republic: comparison of the Bohemian Massif and Western Carpathians.

1. Studies of slope movements characteristics and particularities in the Bohemian Massif (incl. creeps, slides, flows, steepness in slopes etc) comparing to other European mountains. Analysis of risk of the slope movement and mudslides in the Bohemian Massif.
2. Using cartographic materials, available results of field expeditions of the research group, aerial photographs and satellite images, we plan to demonstrate the area in the Bohemian Massif most affected by landslides (it will be *Map of slope movements in the Western Carpathians and Bohemian Massif*). Analysis of the global climate change on the mountainous region: movement of landmasses, using satellite images and geological field data for different dates.

§ 3. 01. May 2011 – 01. June. Creation of thematic GIS-projects using Arc GIS 9.3

Creation of thematic layers in *ArcGIS 9.3*. Some layers will be downloaded and added into the project from already existing vector sources, others are to be made anew:

- Topographic ground-layer showing relief + satellite images
- Geomorphology
- Hydrogeology and geological layer
- Rivers system
- Distribution of population in mountainous regions of the Czech Republic
- Separate layer showing the high-risk region of natural hazards
- Satellite image of the mountains taken in different time, for analysis of slope dynamics in the past years

All layers will be registered in one topographic coordinate system (geo-referenced) for further using. In this working step we plan to fulfill all necessary image processing, spatial analysis of the thematic layers and creation of new thematic maps showing dynamic of slope movements, using our knowledge from §§ 1-2 and numerous discussions with colleagues.

After creation of separate layers we plan to make a compilation of the results in Layout for printing and preparing the article.

§ 4. 01 June 2011 – 01 July. Modelling and 3D-Mapping

1. Modelling the geomorphological, physical-geographic factors and natural risks in the Bohemian Massif.
Resources: *Spatial Analyst* module (*ArcGIS 9.3*).
2. 3D-Mapping of our region of interest in the Western Carpathians and Bohemian Massif using satellite images and DEM, from Earth Science Data Interface (Internet: <http://glcfapp.umiacs.umd.edu:8080/esdi/index.jsp>)
Resources: *ENVI*-software, or *ArcScene* module in *ArcGIS9.3*.

§ 5. 01. July 2011 – 01. August. Writing the scientific article and final report for the IVF

1. Writing the article for the publication in peer-reviewed scientific journal:
Modelling the dynamic of slope movements in the Bohemian Massif using Arc GIS 9.3 and satellite images (the exact title of the article will be discussed and changed).
2. Preparing the Final report for the IVF.

15 January, 2010.

Scientific chief:
Doc. RNDr. Vít Vilímek, CSc

Visiting student:
Dipl.-Ing. P. Lemenkova

